

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 62

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 62

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 62:0 For the choir director; †according to Jeduthun. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 62:1 לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־יְהוֹתוֹן</p>
<p>Psa. 62:1 "My soul <i>waits</i> in silence for God only; From Him ^bis my salvation. ² He only is my ^arock and my salvation, My ^bstronghold; I shall not be greatly shaken.</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : ² אֵךְ אֵל־ אֱלֹהִים יְהוֹמִיָה נִפְשִׁי כְּמִנִּי יְשׁוּעָתִי : ³ אֵךְ־הוּא צוּרִי וְיְשׁוּעָתִי כְּשֹׁגְבִי לֹא־אֶמּוּט</p>
<p>Psa. 62:3 How long will you assail a man, That you may murder <i>him</i>, all of you, Like a ^aleaning wall, like a tottering fence? ⁴ They have counseled only to thrust him down from his high position; They ^adelight in falsehood; They ^bbless with ¹their mouth, But inwardly they curse. ²Selah.</p>	<p>רַבָּה : ⁴ עַד־אָנָּה אֶתְהוֹתְתוּ עַל אִישׁ אֶתְרָצְחוּ כְּלַיְכֶם כְּקִיר נָטוּי וְיִדָּר הַדְּחוּיָהּ : ⁵ אֵךְ מִשְׁאֵתוֹ יַעֲצוּ לְהַדִּיחַ יָרְצוּ כָזָב בְּפִי יְבָרְכוּ וְיִבְקְרֶכֶם יִקְלְלוּ־סִלָּה : ⁶ אֵךְ לְאֱלֹהִים יְהוֹמִי נִפְשִׁי כִי־ כְּמִנִּי תִקְוֶתִי : ⁷ אֵךְ־הוּא צוּרִי וְיְשׁוּעָתִי כְּשֹׁגְבִי לֹא־אֶמּוּט : ⁸</p>
<p>Psa. 62:5 My soul, ^await in silence for God only, For my hope is from Him. ⁶ He only is ^amy rock and my salvation, My stronghold; I shall not be shaken. ⁷ On God my ^asalvation and my glory <i>rest</i>; The rock of my strength, my ^brefuge is in God. ⁸ "Trust in Him at all times, O people;</p>	<p>עַל־אֱלֹהִים יִשְׁעֵי וְכְבוֹדִי צוּר־ עֵינִי כְּמַחְסֵי בְּאֱלֹהִים : ⁹ בְּטַחֲוֹ בּוֹ בְּכָל־עֵת אֵעָם שִׁפְכוּ־לִפְנָיו לְבַבְכֶם אֱלֹהִים מִחֲסֵה־לָנוּ סִלָּה : ¹⁰ אֵךְ אִתְּבַל בְּנֵי־אָדָם כָּזָב בְּנֵי אִישׁ בְּמֵאזְנַיִם לְעֵלוֹת הַמָּה מִתְּבַל יָחַד : ¹¹ אֵל־ תְּבַטְחוּ בְּעִשְׂקֹ וּבְגִזְלֵ אֵל־ תִּתְהַבְּלוּ תִיל אִכִּי־יָנוּב אֵל־ תְּשִׁיתוּ לֵב : ¹² אַחַת וְיִדָּר</p>

^bPour out your heart before Him;
God is a refuge for us. Selah.

Psa. 62:9 Men of ^alow degree are only
^bvanity and men of rank are a ¹lie;
In the ^abalances they go up;
They are together lighter than
breath.

¹⁰ ^aDo not trust in oppression
And do not ¹vainly hope in
^brobbery;
If riches increase, ^cdo not set *your*
heart *upon them*.

Psa. 62:11 ¹Once God has ^aspoken;
²Twice I have heard this:
That ^bpower belongs to God;
¹² And lovingkindness ^ais Yours, O
Lord,
For You ^brecompense a man
according to his work.

אֱלֹהִים שִׁתִּים-נָו שָׁמַעְתִּי כִּי עֹז
לְאֱלֹהִים : 13 וְלֹךְ-אֲדַנִּי חֶסֶד
כִּי-אַתָּה תִשְׁלַם לְאִישׁ
כַּמַּעֲשָׂהוּ :

References

Psalm 62:0

†Cf 1 Chr 16:41; 25:1; Ps 39 and titles

Psalm 62:1

^aPs 33:20

^bPs 37:39

Psalm 62:2

^aPs 89:26

^bPs 59:17; 62:6

Psalm 62:3

^aIs 30:13

Psalm 62:4

¹Lit *bis*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 4:2

^bPs 28:3; 55:21

Psalm 62:5

^aPs 62:1

Psalm 62:6

^aPs 62:2

Psalm 62:7

^aPs 85:9; Jer 3:23

^bPs 46:1

Psalm 62:8

^aPs 37:3, 5; 52:8; Is 26:4

^{b1} Sam 1:15; Ps 42:4; Lam 2:19

Psalm 62:9

^aPs 49:2

^bJob 7:16; Ps 39:5; Is 40:17

^cPs 116:11

^dIs 40:15

Psalm 62:10

¹Lit *become vain in robbery*

^aIs 30:12

^bIs 61:8; Ezek 22:29; Nah 3:1

^jJob 31:25; Ps 49:6; 52:7; Mark 10:24; Luke 12:15; 1 Tim 6:10

Psalm 62:11

¹Or *One thing*

²Or *These two things I have heard*

^aJob 33:14; 40:5

^bPs 59:17; Rev 19:1

Psalm 62:12

^aPs 86:5; 103:8; 130:7

^bJob 34:11; Ps 28:4; Jer 17:10; Matt 16:27; Rom 2:6; 1 Cor 3:8; Rev 2:23

Targum

Psa. 62:1 For praise, by Jeduthun. A psalm of David. ² Truly, for God my soul is quiet; from him is my redemption. ³ Truly, he is my strength and my redemption, my savior, I shall not be shaken on the day of great distress. ⁴ How long do you rage against a pious man? All of you will be slain, like a crooked wall, like a broken fence. ⁵ Truly, when they swear to do good, they take counsel to attack; they will tell lies; with their mouth they will bless and with their heart they will curse forever. ⁶ Truly, be silent for God, O my soul, for my hope comes from him. ⁷ Truly, he is my strength and my redemption, my savior, I shall not be shaken. ⁸ My redemption and my honor is on God; the strength of my might, my hope, is in God. ⁹ Hope in his word at all times, O people of the house of Israel; pour out the pride of your hearts in his presence; say, "God is our hope forever." ¹⁰ For the sons of men are nothing, the sons of a man are deceit; when they take wives, their fates are weighed in the balances; they themselves came to be altogether out of nothing. ¹¹ Do not trust in oppression, and do not receive money gained by coercion; for [though] it will increase in value, do not set your mind [on it]. ¹² God speaks one Torah, and now two times I have heard it, from the mouth of Moses, the great scribe, for there is might in the presence of God. ¹³ And it is yours, O God, to show favor to the righteous, for you repay each man according to his works.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

David was being pursued by his enemies, who were set on killing him. Even in the face of these enemies, David never lost hope or faith that the LORD would take care of him. The enemies were wealthy people who could buy murderers to kill David. David's faith demonstrates that it is best to have faith in the LORD and not in money or riches. The sage Rashi calls this Psalm the hymn of Israel during the Exile.

Superscript

According to Rabbi Hirsch יְדֻתוֹן is not the name of a person. He compared the Hebrew word structure and noted that it is the same as Psalm 77. If this is a name, it is not easy to understand his relationship with David. This name can be found in 1 Chronicles 16:41-42. It is not clear from this passage if Jeduthun was the choir director. Therefore, Hirsch believes that Jeduthun is not a name.

יְדֻתוֹן (ydeeton) root word means "hand" and, in its form, denotes the activity of the hand. It means the eternally constant Divine providence as demonstrated in the fate of individuals.

To the Sefirah Netzach who gives victory over an enemy, upon the providences of God's hand, a psalm of David.

Verse one

The basic theme of the Psalm is that even when the hand of the LORD strikes us with pain and sorrow, we can turn to none but Him for comfort. The LORD is always a source of help.

Only toward God does my soul wait in silence; my salvation comes from Him.

Verse two

He is my rock, my salvation, and my stronghold; I shall not be significantly swayed.

Verse three

This is a difficult verse to interpret. It contains several words that are only found in this Psalm in their grammatical format. Hirsch offers the following translation.

How long will you seek to strike terror into a man, as if all of you were threatened by murder as if the mere leaning of a wall, the fence has already been cast down?

Verse four

לְהַדְּעָהוּ – Phadeecha, “to induce a person to deviate from the right path.”

They have plotted only to lure him down from his lofty station; they have chosen deceit; they bless with his speech but curse within their hearts. Meditate on this verse.

Verses five & six

David firmly repeats that he will not stray from the LORD no matter what happens.

The LORD is the sole source of David's peace of mind for that day and every day. Only before God be silent, my soul, for my hope comes from him.

He alone is my Rock and my Salvation, my stronghold, and I shall certainly not be swayed.

Verse seven

In the light of danger and possible death, David calls out to the LORD for help. All of his hopes will always rest with the LORD.

With God is my salvation and my glory; the rock of my fortitude and my refuge is in God.

Verse eight

David envisioned himself in the "school of suffering." He wanted to tell all his people the conviction that he learned that the LORD is in charge even in suffering.

Trust in the LORD at all times, O people; pour out your hearts before Him; God is a refuge unto us. Meditate upon this passage.

Verse nine

The LORD is always with his people. He is unchangeable, regardless of whether He blesses us with joy or afflicts us with grief.

However, the sons of man are to no purpose, and the sons of men are deceitful; all of them together can be made to spring up by a breath upon the scales.

Verse ten

You cannot look toward humans for help because, most times you will not receive any. Therefore, put your trust in the LORD, who will protect you and your property.

Put not your trust in property unlawfully withheld nor make yourselves as naughty by robbery; even when your riches flourish in accord with right, set not your heart upon them.

Verses eleven & twelve

David learned two lessons. First is that the LORD is invincible in His might; second, the LORD is unchangeable.

One thing has God spoken; I have heard this dual truth therein; that steadfastness belongs to God.

And that to You, my Master, it is mercy when You reward every man in accordance with his acts.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who gives victory over an enemy, upon the providences of God's hand, a psalm of David.

Only toward God does my soul wait in silence; my salvation comes from Him. He is my rock, my salvation, and my stronghold; I shall not be significantly swayed.

How long will you seek to strike terror into a man, as if all of you were threatened by murder as if the mere leaning of a wall, the fence has already been cast down?

They have plotted only to lure him down from his lofty station; they have chosen deceit; they bless with his speech but curse within their hearts. Meditate on this verse.

The LORD is the sole source of David's peace of mind for that day and every day. Only before God be silent, my soul, for my hope comes from him.

He alone is my Rock and my Salvation, my stronghold, and I shall certainly not be swayed.

With God is my salvation and my glory; the rock of my fortitude and my refuge is in God.

Trust in the LORD at all times, O people; pour out your hearts before Him; God is a refuge unto us. Meditate upon this passage.

However, the sons of man are to no purpose, and the sons of men are deceitful; all of them together can be made to spring up by a breath upon the scales.

Put not your trust in property unlawfully withheld nor make yourselves as naughty by robbery; even when your riches flourish in accord with right, set not your heart upon them.

One thing has God spoken; I have heard this dual truth therein; that steadfastness belongs to God.

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Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

